

Srijal's Law of Energy Safety

Srijal Dutta

Independent Researcher

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As systems grow more powerful, compact, and autonomous, *managing energy-related risk* becomes increasingly critical. Traditional safety metrics are domain-specific, and often reactive. This paper introduces a simple but powerful concept – the *Safety Constant*, which quantitatively captures the relationship between energy, risk and the safety infrastructure.

This approach offers a *universal* metric to evaluate whether a system is safe enough, dangerous, or critically unstable – regardless of its domain.

Formula Definition

Base Law

$$S_c = \frac{E_d \cdot R_f}{S_f}$$

Where,

S_c = Safety Constant

E_d = Energy Density

R_f = Risk Factor

S_f = Safety Factor

Risk Factor Decomposition

$$R_f = P_r \cdot S_v$$

Where,

P_r = Probability of Failure

S_v = Severity

Final Expression

The final Expression is as follows

$$S_c = \frac{E_d \cdot P_r \cdot S_v}{S_f}$$

Interpretation Table

S_c Value	Status	Meaning	Design Action
$x < 0.3$	VERY SAFE	Large safety margin	May consider reducing safety equipment to cut costs
$0.3 < x < 0.6$	SAFE	Balanced Risk & Containment	Maintain/Try to reach
$0.6 \leq x \leq 1$	TOP LIMIT	Safety Threshold	Caution
$1.0 \leq x \leq 1.5$	RISKY	High Energy/Low Containment	Treat with high caution/redesign
$1.5 < x < 2.0$	DANGEROUS	Failure Likely	Redesign mandatory
$x \geq 2$	CRITICAL	Catastrophic Failure Possible	Shutdown/Recall immediately

Limitations

- Subjectivity in estimating P_r and S_v .
- Cannot capture quantum anomalies or non-energy-based risks
- Real-world safety involves complex redundancy not modeled by a single S_f .